

Usability Experts (1): Designers (0).

Why designers need to evaluate design effectiveness

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Abstract:

The limitations of design evaluation methods continue to hinder designers working in commercial website design practice. Relatively little is known about evaluating website design beyond usability and basic affective response to aesthetics, nor about the impact of user-testing on design innovation or strategic design goals related to emotion. It is suggested that the lack of designer input into the development of testing metrics for design evaluation has contributed to a limited testing methodology for evaluating website effectiveness. Furthermore, it is suggested that a lack of designer involvement in design evaluation has contributed to perceptions that designers are ‘stylists’ rather than strategists, undermining design as a profession. It is argued, that for this situation to change, designers must actively participate in the evaluation of website design effectiveness and in the research and development of evaluation methods.

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Background

The development of client-commissioned government, public institution and large-scale corporate websites is generally driven by a user-centered design paradigm. Consequently, websites are often subjected to user-testing in order to evaluate usability and validate design decisions. Proponents of user-testing argue that design evaluation is a critical part of what should be an iterative, cyclical process, occurring throughout the development process (e.g. Kuniavsky, 2003; Preece, 2002; Wania et al, 2006). Critics of user-testing however, argue that in practice too much emphasis has been placed on usability, performance and efficiency, while neglecting the entirety of the user experience, particularly emotional response (e.g. Haig, 2002; Hassenzahl, 2004; Hassenzahl and

Tractinsky, 2006; Hekkert, 2006; Lavie and Tractinsky, 2004; Lenker, 2002; Lindgaard and Fernandes, 2006; Park, 2004; Tractinsky et al, 2000, 2006).

Concerns about the limitations of user-testing methods, particularly usability testing, have prompted a growing number of researchers to investigate the role of aesthetics and emotions within human-computer interaction (HCI). Frequently referred to as *user experience design*, this area of research is perceived as an alternative to traditional, usability-focused HCI. (Hassenzahl and Tractinsky, 2006). Of relevance to web designers, is literature published in this area, that addresses the following concerns:

- General argument about the importance and role of emotions in HCI, the need to evaluate all aspects of user-experience, and the associated complexities of evaluating emotional response (e.g. Görtz, 2007; Hudlicka, 2003; Picard, 2003; Picard and Daily, 2005; Wiberg, 2003)
- Investigation of methods/metrics suitable for evaluating users' emotional response – particularly psychophysiological testing – and associated issues (e.g. Boehner et al., 2007; Chateau and Mersiol, 2004; Hazlett and Benedek, 2007; Isbister et al., 2007; Morris and Turner, 2001)
- The relationship between design aesthetics and usability, and relevance of aesthetics to users' experiences of interactive media (e.g. Bernard et al, 2000; Haig, 2002; Hassenzahl, 2004; Kim et al., 2003; Lavie and Tractinsky, 2004; Lindgaard and Fernandes, 2006; Mahlke and Lindgaard, 2007; Marsico and Leviaidi, 2003; Pandir and Knight, 2006; Park et al., 2004; Schenkman and Jonsson, 2000; Tractinsky et al., 2000, 2006).

Conceded by many researchers, is that the evaluation of emotional response to interactive media design is complex, and that research in this area is in its infancy.

Issues associated with user-testing and the evaluation of website design effectiveness

There are a number of evaluation methods commonly used to assess websites in a commercial context. These include: questionnaires, focus groups, think-aloud procedure, retrospective probing, usability testing, cognitive walkthroughs, and heuristics. (Kuniavsky, 2003). Although these methods provide insight into the user experience, they also have limitations – particularly when used to evaluate emotional response. Also of

relevance to practicing web designers, are difficulties in ascertaining the relationship between emotional response and specific design elements – making the task of evaluating website design effectiveness, somewhat problematic (Kim et al., 2003; Lindgaard and Fernandes, 2006).

Compounding these issues, is the fact that the relationship between design and the evaluation process is itself under-researched and therefore not well understood (Wania et al, 2006). Of concern too, for designers, is that relatively little is known about the impact of current user-testing practices on the development of emotionally engaging, innovative websites.

Issues with usability testing

Arguably, the method most frequently used to evaluate website design, is usability testing. In addition to perceived limitations inherent with this method (i.e. failure to address underlying emotional needs of users), questions have been raised about the validity of a number of usability studies (Gray and Salzman, 1998; Hornbaek, 2006).

Hornbaek (2006), in his review of over 180 studies published in HCI journals and proceedings, concluded that “in many studies, the choice of and reasoning about usability measures fall short of a valid and reliable account of usability as quality-in-use of the user interface being studied”. Information provided was often hard to link to specific parts of interface or interaction, and measures of quality of interaction, e.g. assessment by domain experts, were rarely used.

It would be erroneous to suggest that usability is not beneficial for creating user-friendly websites. However, despite industry dependence on usability-testing, little, if any research has been conducted to determine the extent to which usability testing impacts on designer intent and the achievement of strategic design goals – particularly those related to emotional design.

Issues with evaluating user experience

Researchers and designers, frustrated by perceived limitations of usability-oriented user-studies, have readily embraced the terms *user experience* (Hassenzahl and Tractinsky, 2006) and *experience design* (e.g. Shedroff, 2002). Hassenzahl and Tractinsky define user

experience as being “a consequence of a user’s internal state (predispositions, expectations, needs, motivation, mood, etc.), the characteristics of the designed system (e.g. complexity, purpose, usability, functionality, etc.) and the context (or the environment) within which the interaction occurs (e.g. organisational/social setting, meaningfulness of the activity, voluntariness of use, etc.)”. Despite the appeal of ‘user experience’ as a design ethos, Hassenzahl and Tractinsky observe that while it is “well-discussed at conferences and symposia, that it only rarely enters the relevant academic journals”. They suggest that this may be due to the absence of empirical research, and that this serves as an impediment to the further development and understanding of user experience.

While a few researchers have specifically addressed the evaluation of emotional response to website design, the majority of investigations to date, appear to have been conducted within the context of theoretical research rather than commercial website development (e.g. Görtiz, 2007; Haig, 2002; Kim et al., 2003; Marsico and Levialdi, 2003; Park et al., 2004, 2005; Schenkman and Jonsson, 2000; Tractinsky et al., 2000, 2006). Haig also suggests that: “many of the sites evaluated (and constructed) by non-designers researching the field of Web site design could have the ... criticism (lack of appropriateness to their context) leveled at their selection of sites, and the design of their sites”. If this is indeed the case, it raises questions about the validity and applicability of research findings to commercial practice.

Evidence of design evaluation being conducted by designers

A review of peer-reviewed design journals reveals few articles containing in-depth discussion of design evaluation. Articles that do address design evaluation methods and metrics tend to originate from the field of industrial or product design. While a number of design researchers have advocated a user-centered approach to design – including a few from the communication/multimedia design disciplines¹ – the majority appear to be more concerned with addressing a philosophical debate about the nature of design research and broader methodological issues, rather than the intricacies of design decision-making

¹ It should be noted, that for the purpose of this paper, the term ‘(website) designers’ is used to refer to ‘communication’ designers working across both print-based and electronic media, as well as ‘multimedia’ and designers, who work predominantly with electronic media – including websites.

processes and methods and metrics for evaluating design effectiveness (e.g.: Bayazit 2004; Conley, 2004; Forlizzi and Lebbon, 2002; Hanington, 2003; Postma and Stappers, 2006; Redström, 2006; Richardson, 1993; Roth, 1999; Sato, 2004; Strickler, 1999). Case studies cited as providing evidence of the successfulness of a user-centred design approach in communication design tend to be lacking in detail with regard to the impact of evaluation methods and metrics on the design process. Furthermore, in some instances where user-testing is used during the design process, evaluation of the final design outcome is not conducted (e.g: Hanington, 2003; Forlizzi and Lebbon, 2002; Postma and Stappers, 2006). It is suggested that this may indicate a lack of rigor in the evaluation process or under-reporting of case studies, particularly when compared to the degree of evidence provided in the peer-reviewed publications of other disciplines such as HCI.

The lack of evidence of design evaluation being undertaken by communication designers is perhaps unsurprising. Hassenzahl and Tractinsky (2006) state that although evaluation and design are interdependent, that the two in practice, are separate.

To date there has been no publication written by, or aimed specifically at, communication and/or multimedia designers, on the subject of evaluating design effectiveness. Published books on design research methods (e.g. Noble and Bestley, 2005; Viscocky O'Grady et al, 2006) focus on broader methodological issues and introduction of various user-testing methods, rather than providing detailed analyses of the application of methods and metrics for the purpose of design evaluation in commercial design practice. Existing books that do discuss user-testing methods and metrics in detail (e.g. Kuniavsky, 2003; Rubin, 1994), are not written from the perspective of the designer, and do not address the complexities of evaluating design iterations in relation to the achievement of emotion- or experience-related design goals.

The case of the usability experts versus the designers – a cautionary tale

During the developmental years of the Internet (late 1990s – early 2000's) most critical discussion in the mainstream media with regard to web design, including published books, emanated not from designers, but from usability and accessibility proponents (e.g. Flanders and Willis, 1998; Flanders and Peters, 2002; Krug, 2000; Nielsen, 2000a; Nielsen and Tahir 2002) – although there were rare exceptions (e.g. Lenker, 2002).

Arguably the most widely quoted in the mass media², was ‘usability expert’ Jakob Nielsen – a software engineer.

Designers – purveyors of evil?

Perhaps the most widely condemned practice, favoured by many designers, was the use of Flash technology for the creation of entire websites, as well as animated introductory web or splash pages^{3 4}. For designers, Flash technology, introduced by Macromedia in 1996, presented opportunities to create immersive and emotionally engaging online experiences using animation, sound and video. For communication designers moving into website design, and used to the immutability of the printed page, it also meant not having to contend with the design limitations of HTML.

One of the most comprehensive studies of Flash usability undertaken, done by Loranger and Nielsen of the Nielsen Norman Group (2002), tested the usability of 46 Flash applications. These were evaluated on ‘feature success’ (if users completed parts of a task unassisted) and ‘task success’ (if users completed tasks unassisted). The study determined the average ‘feature success’ rate of the applications was 64%, while the average ‘task success’ was just 45% – indicating usability problems with the Flash applications tested. They suggested, that while Flash technology offers the prospect of functionality beyond reading and browsing, that in practice the ‘broader set of design options usually translate into more rope for hanging the users.’ (Loranger and Nielsen, 2002)

Complaints leveled at Flash by Nielsen (2000b) include: gratuitous animation; resemblance to television rather than interactive media; introduction of non-standard

² Source: www.useit.com/jakob/. Retrieved 6 May 2008.

³ “Flash is the favorite toy of big designer studios and numerous amateur graphic artists alike. Flash is visually attractive, and in general attractive websites are more successful than the ugly ones ... But this is not the case of Flash websites.”
Source: www.seoresearcher.com/seo-flash-is-evil-five-big-reasons-not-to-use-flash.htm. Retrieved 19 June 2008.

⁴ Vincent Flanders states: “Designers are still making their pages too big, they're using Flash in the wrong places, using splash pages at all... the usual mistakes designers have been making forever.”
Source: www.sitepoint.com/print/flanders-web-pages-suck. Retrieved 19 June 2008.

controls; inability to change font size; superficiality of content; inability to conduct site searches; and, non-adherence to HTML conventions. Rather than providing a means for designers to create more emotionally engaging experiences, Flash instead became synonymous with unusable and inaccessible website design – as did designers, by association.

Has usability testing impacted negatively on the development of the Internet?

Vincent Flanders, while critical of Internet designers, states: “Designers don’t like usability because making a site usable is boring and designers hate being bored – a fact I can heartily identify with. The truth is, commercial Web design has become really, really boring. The exciting stuff is all experimental...” (Laidlaw, 2002)

Whether or not usability testing has had a negative impact on the overall development of the World Wide Web as an emotionally engaging medium, is a question that cannot be readily answered. Much of the web’s design history has been lost, due to its highly ephemeral and constantly evolving nature. If commercial web design has indeed become boring, as suggested by Flanders, perhaps this is the result of a natural process of ‘convergence’, from the diversity of early design ‘experiments’ towards user-friendly, prototypical design ‘ideals’. If however, it is simply reflective of delivering more of what users are already familiar with and have come to expect – does have consequences for designers attempting to engage audiences at an emotional level through innovative design?

The following website example is not provided with the intention of answering this question, but rather to provide food for thought.

The Sydney Opera House Virtual Tour (2001)

The *Sydney Opera House Virtual Tour* (Figures 1 and 2) was a Flash application produced by the Sydney Opera House Trust, to enable viewers to explore the Opera House online. It generated online visits numbering in the millions, was hailed a ‘success story’ by Adobe, and was described by Apple as “one of the finest tours you’ll ever take without a docent.”^{5 6}

Figure 1: Sydney Opera House Virtual Tour ⁷

⁵ The *Sydney Opera House Virtual Tour* was described in an Apple News Release (2001) as follows: “If you’d like to see inside Australia’s magnificent Sydney Opera House, just follow the bouncing yellow ball. □ □ This animated device leads you into an extraordinary new virtual tour created by the Sydney Opera House Trust. Their award-winning website combines Macromedia Flash and QuickTime VR to provide a clever integration of panoramas, maps, animations, and pop-up information kiosks.” Source: www.apple.com/eneews/2001/03/23eneews3.html#top. Retrieved 5 August, 2008.

⁶ ‘Adobe Success Story’ – Sydney Opera House: Within two days of launching the Virtual Tour (March 2001), developer Tony David Cray received 150 emails from people around the world. “In the second week, the response was so overwhelming, that the site required a dedicated server to handle the volume of traffic it was attracting. Within three weeks, it had been exposed to an estimated market of 650 million people worldwide and had received numerous accolades.” Source: www.adobe.com/cfusion/showcase/index.cfm?event=casestudydetail&casestudyid=2232&loc=en_us. Retrieved 4 August, 2008.

⁷ Source (top): culturegap.files.wordpress.com/2007/07/the_sydney_opera_house_virtual_tour.jpeg

Figure 2: Sydney Opera House Virtual Tour ⁸

Project manager Tony David Cray’s goal was to provide both information and a ‘behind-the-scenes’ experience for visitors. “There was a real hunger among the public for information about the building, but there was no easy way to get it. There were books, but nothing that gave the immersive sensation of being there.” ⁹

The Virtual Tour was also one of 46 Flash applications tested by Loranger and Nielsen (2002). The task scenario, undertaken by testers to evaluate the tour’s usability, was to find the locations of the Bennelong Restaurant and the Playhouse, in order to ascertain the time required to get between the restaurant and theatre, prior to seeing a show.

Testing revealed several usability issues. Loranger and Nielsen noted, that although the tour contained a lot of useful information, that most people ‘were overwhelmed by the complexity of the site and didn’t know where to begin or what the icons meant’. Criticism was particularly directed at the yellow bouncing balls, which revealed the name of locations on rollover. They suggested: ‘People were more successful at finding locations on a well-labeled static map than on a complex interactive one. It would have been more helpful if developers had cut back on the fancy interaction and labeled the locations.’ Despite achieving an 80% ‘feature success rate’, the ‘task success’ rating was just 40%.

⁸ Source: www.melbpc.org.au/pcupdate/2107/2107article6.htm

⁹ Source: as Footnote 6.

The Sydney Opera Location Map (2008)

The Virtual Tour is no longer accessible on the Sydney Opera House website. Visitors instead can access a 3-D House Map (Figure 3) – which is also a Flash application. Its visual style is simpler than that of the Virtual Tour, and includes location labels. Clicking on the labels brings up highlighted areas on the map, clearly showing users the location of facilities within the Opera House and related information. Photographs are not included.

Figure 3: Sydney Opera House House Map ¹⁰

¹⁰ Source: www.sydneyoperahouse.com/visit/precinct_map.aspx. Retrieved 18 August, 2008.

The emotional experience

As noted earlier, the Virtual Tour is no longer accessible online, making it difficult for independent researchers to determine with any certainty, differences in the quality of emotional experience when interacting with the two applications.

It is not known whether the current House Map was produced as a direct the result of user testing conducted by Loranger and Nielsen, however it appears to address usability issues identified by them. While the House Map may address the practical needs of users who have the same sort of task-oriented goal, as tested for by Loranger and Nielsen, it could be suggested that the emotional needs of a some internet visitors may not be met. For users, whose goal it is to explore and discover this ‘masterpiece of creativity’¹¹ for themselves, the omission of the photographic panoramas and difference in design style, may not facilitate the same level of immersion intended by Cray.

Figure 4: Sydney Opera House ¹²

¹¹ The Sydney Opera House is on the UNESCO World Heritage List. A report by the International Council on Monuments and Sites to the World Heritage Committee describes the Opera House as “one of the indisputable masterpieces of human creativity, not only in the 20th century but in the history of humankind.”

Source: www.sydneyoperahouse.com/about/house_history_landing.aspx. Retrieved 10 August 2008

¹² Source: http://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/Image:Sydney_Opera_House_Sails.jpg

Leaving aside speculation as to the reason for the demise of the Virtual Tour, there are two causes for concern for designers. The first is the apparent limitations of the testing conducted by Loranger and Nielsen, which appeared to evaluate only one of two major design goals identified by Cray (i.e. provision of information). The second major design goal – the provision of an immersive emotional experience – was not evaluated.

The second cause for concern is the apparent discrepancy between the usability testing results on the one hand, and industry accolades and site popularity on the other. While industry accolades may simply be reflective of marketing strategies of software companies, the reported popularity of the site suggests a degree of success not reflected in the testing. These two points raise questions about the nature of testing and its potential to impact adversely on website development.

The need for designers to get involved in design evaluation

The relative lack of literature on the subject of website design evaluation by designers, indicates that designers have offered little in the way of empirical evidence to challenge the findings and arguments of usability specialists. While it may be tempting for designers to simply leave design evaluation to others, it could be suggested that this may be detrimental to design practice. Designers may claim that the lack of designer involvement in design evaluation is largely due to lack of demand by clients. However it is argued, that even though there may be little scope for job-specific evaluative research in some instances, there is a professional need to demonstrate the effectiveness of what designers ‘do’ – despite the inherent complexities.

The need for designers to become design evaluation methodologists

Four years ago, Conley (2004) posed the question: “Where are the design methodologists?” Conley argued for the development of ‘methods that are explicit, useful and whose efficacy can be measured’ as being ‘essential for the development of design as a discipline’ and its evolution from a craft to a ‘field’. Similar sentiments have been expressed by other design researchers, who have also argued for a more systematic development, understanding and rigorous application of design research methods (e.g. Forlizzi and Lebbon 2002; Nemeth 2003; Poggenpohl 2003; Roth 1999). Poggenpohl (2004) argues, “Design, a weak discipline, is at a disadvantage in inter-disciplinary work,

if considered from a traditional academic perspective. Its body of knowledge is not well established in contrast to other disciplines”.

Conclusion

It is suggested that there is a need for designers to become active, if reluctant, participants in the research of design evaluation methods. Regardless of whether designers agree in principle with the empirical evaluation of design, Internet design is evaluated. By failing to engage in debate as to what constitutes good web design with usability proponents, and by not critically analysing the appropriateness of testing methods for Internet design, designers have – perhaps unwittingly – contributed to a lack of understanding as to how best to evaluate all aspects of the user-experience. It is suggested, that it is timely for practicing web designers to set their own research agenda.

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